

Timeline Picture Created Using Microsoft Word

Normal first pregnancy of previously healthy women

Male, 30 weeks of gestation, birth weight 660g

Respiratory failure, congenital sepsis

Bronchopulmonary dysplasia, feeding disorders

Discharged home, body weight 2,560g

Female, 27 weeks and 4 days of gestation, birth weight 470 g

Respiratory failure

Liver failure, hepatosplenomegaly, coagulopathy.
Peculiar phenotype, suspicion of metabolic or
chromosomal diseases.

Birth of child B

First months of life

Age of 2.5 month

Age of 4 years

Birth of child A

Age of 1 month and 16 days

Age of 7 months and 7 days

Emergency caesarean section, intubated shortly after birth

Follow up - non-allergic asthma, behavioral problems

Emergency caesarean section, intubated immediately after
birth

Medical genetic testing were found to be normal.

Collection of blood samples:
Child-A – post mortem.
Child B – 4 years old

Death of child A due to pulmocardial insufficiency